
Control Of Sugarcane Woolly Aphids *Ceratovacuna Laniger* By Biocontrol Agents

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Abstract:

Sugarcane woolly aphids *Ceratovacuna lanigera* Zehnter was first reported in West Bengal in 1958, then spread in other part of Northeastern region. Woolly aphids was first noticed in Sangli District in July 2002 and then spread subsequently other districts of Western Maharashtra and then spread in Marathwada and Vidarbha region. As far as Western Maharashtra is concerned woolly aphid infestation was seen since 2002 in various proportions and causes serious damage to sugarcane ultimately yield and sugar recovery were decreased so far. Patan tahsil situated in range of Sahyadri; due to climatic changes the ecological condition were favorable for infestation of woolly aphids. The infestation of woolly aphids was observed continuously last ten years in the belt of Koyana river.

I have surveyed predators on the woolly aphid, viz. *Dipha aphidivora* (Meyrick), *Micromus igorotus* (Banks), *Eupeodes confrater* (Wiedmann), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens), Lady Bird beetles, spiders, etc. Of which larvae *Eupeodes confrater* and *Dipha aphidivora* were consumed large number of aphids in their life span and also effective during dry condition. Keeping in view, the attempt has been made on record of biocontrol agent of woolly aphids.

Keywords: Sugarcane, Woolly Aphid, Biocontrol Agent etc.

Introduction:

Sugarcane and sugar beet are the two main sources of white crystal sugar in the world and sugarcane contributes about 70 %. Worldwide sugarcane occupies an area of 20.1 m. ha. with a total production of 1318.1 m. t. at a productivity rate of 65.5 tons per ha. India contribute 20.4 % area (4.32 m ha) and 18.6 % of production (2.70 m. t.) and ranks second among the sugarcane growing countries of the world in both area and production. In country, it is an important cash crop which shares 7 % of total value of agricultural output occupying only 2.8 % of gross cropped area. The sugar industry with more than 450 sugar factories in operation is the second largest agro based industry in India next to cotton textile industry (Anon, 2005).

As many as 125 species of insects are known to infest sugarcane as major pests in various parts of the world which are causing economic loss to the extent of 20 % in yield and 15 % in sugar recovery. In India, the crop withstand more than 289 different pests. Out of which 213 are insects. Of these 20 species have been considered as major pests on sugarcane including moths, bobbers termites, white grubs, scale insects, pyrilla, white flies, mealy bugs, army worm etc. (Likhil, 2006). The severe outbreak of *Ceratovacuna lanigera* Zehnter is a new addition to the major pest category causing severe losses in cane yield and sugar recovery during last three years (Patil, 2004).

According to Raychaudhuri (1984), more than 15 species of aphids associated

with the sugarcane in India of which seven species belongs to subfamily Aphididae, five from Pemphiginae, three from Hormaphidinae and one from Drepanosiphinae. Subfamily Hormaphidinae, *Ceratovacuna lagigera* is serious pest of sugarcane noticed in India and oriental region.

Infestation of woolly aphids was present either side of midrib under surface of sugarcane leaves and then spread over entire leaves. Woolly aphid is economically important groups of insects since they cause the damage to sugarcane by sucking by sucking the cell sap from leaves. As a result, white yellowish spots develop on the leaves, which becomes brittle and gradually dry completely. Aphids continuously excreting copious honey dew, which create sooty moulds on the leaves. Continuously infestation leads to reduction in length and weight of the cane as well as sugar content of the sap (Jadhav and Sathe 2010).

Due infestation of woolly aphids severe losses in cane yield and sugar recovery. The losses to the tune of 26 % in yield and 24 % in sugar content have been reported (Shankar and Shitole, 2004). In Maharashtra 7 to 39 % reduction in cane yield and 1.2 to 3.43 unit reduction in sugar recovery has been reported. A total loss of about Rs.874 crores has been estimated in India due to damage caused by Sugarcane woolly aphids (Patil *et.al* 2004b).

Woolly aphids are less mobile and found on ventral surface of leaves where chemical couldn't reach to control the pest in usual manner. Under such condition application of biocontrol agents play an important role in the control of woolly aphid up to certain level. Without any harm to the crop and environment, maximum degree of success have been achieved by biological control agents such as *Dipha aphidivora* (Meyrick), *Micromus igorotus* (Banks), *Eupeodes confrater* (Wiedmann), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens), Lady bird

beetles, spider etc. Of which larvae *Eupeodes confrater* and *Dipha aphidivora* were consumed large number of aphids in their life span and also effective during dry condition while *Micromus* only active in rainy season during cool and cloudy climate. Apart from that, we noted larvae of lady bird beetle spiders etc. on the woolly aphids (Blachsmith Blackman and Eastop, 2000).

Materials and Methods:

Survey was carried out in the selected spots of study area of Patan tahsil of Satara district in Maharashtra during rainy season up to month of January in 2020 and 2022 for study the biocontrol agents of woolly aphids on sugarcane. The observation were made at morning and evening time at 15 days interval and adopted one man one hour search technique. During survey observed the variety of biocontrol agents, photograph it's and samples of biocontrol agents were carried out in laboratory. In laboratory study, we had used glass tube, glass beakers and rearing jars for the rearing the larvae of *Dipha aphidivora*, *Micromus igorotus*, *Eupeodes confrater* and *Chrysoperla carnea*. I had provided fresh larvae of sugarcane with woolly aphids to the larvae three times in a days for feeding. I cut the leaves of sugarcane into pieces and count the how many aphids on same. At evening we calculated how many woolly aphids remains in the jar and how many consumed by the larvae. This method continued till formation of pupa. We studied the average feeding potential of larvae of *Dipha divora* (≥ 150), *E. confrater* (120-135), *Micromus igorotus* (42-55) and *Chrysoperla carnea* (65-110) per days. We also studied the biology of the biocontrol agents.

Results and Discussion:

The infestation of white woolly aphids on sugarcane was firstly recorded in west Bengal on (Basu and Banerjee 1958) and then noticed in different part of North

east India. As far as Maharashtra is concerned white woolly aphid was first time recorded in July 2002 in Sangli district (Mote et.al 2003). Subsequently, it spreads in Kolhapur, Satara, Pune, Solapur and Ahmadnagar. Lingappa (2004) noticed woolly aphids spreads at borderline of Karnataka in Athani, Balgaon district in September, 2002 the into other district .Woolly aphids then spreads in Uttar Pradesh , Andra Pradesh, Bihar and Uttarachal stares (Joshi and Viraktamath, 2004).

In last ten years, we observed drastic changes were taken place in the weather parameters hence, changes took place in planting and harvestings of the crops. It causes pest outbreak and affects the yield of the crops. Heavy and discontinuous rain fall, comparatively low temperature high humidity, cool wind and long period of cloudy atmosphere were highly favourable for woolly aphid infestation on sugarcane plant. These conditions were highly favourable in Western part of Maharashtra since last ten to twelve years. Hence, infestation of woolly aphid was found every year in the western parts such as Ajra, Gaganbawada, Radganageri Chandoli, Patan, Medha and Mulasi tahsil of the western Maharashtra in rainy season. Here, the attempt has been made on koyana belt of Patan tahsil of satara district for study of biocontrol agents of woolly aphids (Raychaudhuri, 1984).

During survey biocontrol agent's viz. *Dipha aphidivora*, *Micromus igorotus*, *Eupeodes confrater*, *Chrysoperla carnea* were found on sugarcane woolly aphid of western Maharashtra. We collected larvae and cocoon of *Dipha aphidivora*, *Micromus igorotus*, *Eupeodes confrater* and *Chrysoperla carnea* from infested sugarcane field and carried in laboratory. They provided with fresh infested leaves with woolly aphids every day at morning and evening time and observed the feeding rate

and biology in captivity (Srikanth, et. al, 2015).

Puttannavar et.al (2006) reported that *Conobathra aphidivora* was potential predator of woolly aphid and it has been found to occur in nearly all the areas of from which the aphid has been reported and occasionally has a very substantial effect on the aphid population. A single larva can consume more than 150 aphids / day and about 6000 aphids in its life span and can clear a heavily infested sugarcane leaf with 4000-6000 aphids. During survey we, found that the larva of *Conobathra aphidivora* was very active and voracious feeder on woolly aphid. Female laid whitish /yellowish 70 – 110 eggs on ventral surface of leaf in and around the infestation of woolly aphids. Incubation period was 5-6 days. The larvae had four molts and five instar; entire larval period was 24-35 days. The first instar and second instar was greenish yellow coloured with fine, rare whitish hairs on the body. The duration of first and second instar 2-3 days and 3-5 days respectively. The third, fourth and fifth instar was dark greenish yellow coloured with transverse white strips on the body. The duration of third, fourth and fifth instars was 6-8 days, 8-12 and 5-8 days respectively. Larva secretes whitish silk thread on leaves for protection. In fourth and fifth instar larva become voracious feeder and active. Average single larva consumed 100-150 woolly aphids /day. Pupa was dark brown coloured situated in silk thread secreted by larva. Pupal period was noticed 7- 9 days. Adult male moths survived 1-2 days and female 1-3 days. The entire life cycle completed in one and half month. During survey adult moths of *Dipha* were seen after in sugarcane field at 4 pm and mating took place at night .They were able maintain in dry season .hence more important for control of sugarcane woolly aphids.

Conclusion:

Woolly aphids are less mobile and found on ventral surface of leaves where chemicals couldn't reach to control the pest. Beside these, it causes pollutions and site effects, disturb the cycle in nature and cost effective. Under such condition application of biocontrol agents play an important role in the control of woolly aphid up to certain level. Without any harm to the crop and environment, maximum degree of success have been achieved by biological control agents such as *Dipha aphidivora*, *Micromus igorotus*, *Eupeodes confrater*, *Chrysoperla carnea*, Lady bird beetles and spider etc. During survey found that *Dipha* and Syrphid fly larvae were more effective in control of sugarcane woolly aphid than the larvae of brown lacewing and green lacewing.

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